

Role of Fiberoptic Bronchoscopy in the Diagnosis of Undiagnosed Exudative Pleural Effusion**Rama Prasad Chowdhury¹, Manashjyoti Saikia², Farjana Begum³, Basanta Hazarika⁴**¹Postgraduate Trainee, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital³Assistant Professor, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital⁴Professor & HOD, Dept. of Pulmonary Medicine, Gauhati Medical College Hospital

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Abstract:

Background: Pleuraleffusionis defined as abnormal and excessive accumulation of fluid in pleural space.[1]. Presence of effusion always denotes an underlying pathological process. Due to the diverse causes of pleural effusion establishing the etiology is always challenging. Radiological (CXR, USG, CT), biochemical, cytological and microbiological analysis of the effusion obtained by thoracentesis provides the initial clue. If even after this initial investigation no etiology could be identified, the case is labeled as undiagnosed effusion.

Method: It was an observational study conducted in pulmonary medicine department of Guwahati medical college. Seventy Patients with undiagnosed exudative pleural effusion were subjected to FOB

Results: Thirty four out of 70 patients had FOB findings. 14 patients had endobronchial growth (20%), 4 had mucosal irregularity (5.7%), 16 patients had CBNAAT positive lavage fluid (22.8%). Eighteen out of these 34 patients (52.9%) had haemoptysis. (10 in neoplastic group, 8 in TB group).

Conclusion: FOB may be a useful initial non-invasive tool in undiagnosed exudative pleural effusion before opting for a more invasive procedure like thoracoscopic, which carries a substantially more mortality. The yield of bronchoscopy is more if patient has endobronchial symptom like haemoptysis. So haemoptysis can be an important clinical clue to select patients for FOB.

Keywords: Fiberoptic Bronchoscopy (FOB), Exudative, Pleural Effusion, Haemoptysis, Broncho Alveolar Lavage.

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Introduction

Pleural effusion is defined as the pathological accumulation of fluid in the pleural space [1]. Approximately 20% of pleural effusions remain undiagnosed after evaluation. [2]

Common causes of undiagnosed exudative effusion are malignancy, TB, pulmonary embolism, and parapneumonic effusion particularly anaerobic organism. [3]

Pleural effusion of unknown origin is frequently encountered in tertiary care centre even after completion of exhaustive work-up. Fiberoptic bronchoscopy is useful in the diagnosis of pleural effusion, where at the end of usual work-up, no etiological diagnosis was arrived at. In pleural effusion of unknown origin especially in more than 50 years age group, the contribution of Fiberoptic bronchoscopy in reaching a diagnosis of malignancy is significant. In age group below 50 years with undiagnosed pleural effusion, the contribution of Fiberoptic bronchoscopy in

diagnosing non-malignant causes like Tuberculosis is significant.

Hence, if patients with exudative pleural effusion are still undiagnosed after pleural fluid cytology and with parenchymal abnormalities on chest skiagrams or with history of hemoptysis, Fiberoptic bronchoscopy is a useful procedure for arriving at a diagnosis [4]

Aims and Objectives were to evaluate the role of fiber optic bronchoscopy in the diagnosis of undiagnosed exudative pleural effusion. Exudative pleural effusion with uncertain cause after initial evaluation was included in the study. Children below 18 years and patients unfit for bronchoscopy were excluded from the study.

Methods: The study was conducted between the period of Nov., 2022- July, 2023 in the pulmonary medicine department of Gauhati Medical college. Seventy patients with exudative pleural effusion were evaluated for biochemical (protein, sugar,

ADA, LDH), total count and differential count, malignant cytology (at least one sample and 3 samples where possible) and CBNAAT. Patients in whom no etiology could be diagnosed after initial evaluation, were termed as undiagnosed pleural effusion. These patients were further subjected to fiber optic Bronchoscopy. Result was analysed depending on the FOB findings.

Result

Total 70 patients were included in the study. Fourty eight out of seventy patients were male (68%). Twenty two patients were female (32%) Most

common age group in males was 36 to 55 years constituting 50% of total male patients. Most common age group among female was 46 to 65 years constituting 54.54% of total female patients. Only 2 male patients were in age group 76 to 85(4.16%) and no female patient was in 76-85 age group. Ten male patients (20.83%) were in age group 56-65yrs. Six male (12.5%) patients were in age group 66-75yrs.six male patients(12.5%) in age group 25-35yrs. among females 4 patients (18.18%) were in age group 25-35yrs, 4 patients (18.18%) in 36-45 yr.

Table 1: Gender Distribution

Age	Male (%)	Female (%)	Total (%)
25 to 35	6 (12.5 %)	4 (18.18%)	10 (14.28%)
36 to 45	12 (25%)	6 (27.27 %)	16 (22.85%)
46 to 55	12 (25%)	6 (27.27%)	18 (25.71%)
56 to 65	10 (20.83%)	2 9%)	16 (22.85%)
66 to 75	6 (12.5%)	0 (0 %)	8 (11.42%)
76 to 85	2 (4.16%)	22 (100%)	2 (2.85%)
Total	48 (100%)		70 (100%)

Seventy patients with exudative effusion were evaluated. Right sided pleural effusion was present in 44 patients (62.85%). Left sided effusion was found in 24 patients (34.28%). only 2 patient had bilateral exudative effusion (2.85%)

Table 2: Side of Pleural effusion on Chest X-Ray

Side of Effusion	Numbers	Percentage
Right side	44	62.85%
Left side	24	34.28%
Bilateral	2	2.85%

Figure 1: Side of effusion

Twenty four out of 70 patients (34.2%) had same sided mediastinal shift. Thirty patients had no shift (42.85%) and 16 patients had opposite side mediastinal shift (22.85%). Mediastinal lymphadenopathy was found in 11.42% patients. Infiltrates were found in 17.15% of patients.

Table 3: CT finding

Mediastinal Shift	Numbers	Percentage
Opposite side	16	22.85%
Same Side	24	34.2 %
No Mediastinal Shift	30	42.85 %
Mediastinal Lymph node Infiltrate	8	11.42%
	12	17.15%

Total 70 patients with exudative effusion were included in the study. Straw colour effusion was found in 38 patients (54.28%). Twenty eight patients had hemorrhagic effusion (40%). Only four patients had purulent effusion (5.72%). Forty six patients had ADA value <20(65.71%), 22 had ADA between 20 to 30 (31.42%) and 2 had ADA >30(2.85%). Low peural fluid sugar (<60) was found in 16 patients (23.15%). In 77.85% patients sugar was >60.

Table 4: Pleural fluid analysis

Colour of Pleural Fluid	Numbers	Percentage
Straw colour	38	54.28%
Hemorrhagic	28	40%
Purulent	4	5.72%
Glucose		
>60 mg/dl	54	77.85%
< 60 mg/dl	16	23.15%
ADA		
< 20U/L	46	65.71%
20 to 30 U/L	22	31.42%
>30 U/L	2	2.85%

Seventy patients with undiagnosed effusion were subjected to FOB. Normal bronchoscopy was seen in 24 patients (35%). Fourteen patients (20%) had endobronchial growth, 4 patients (5.71%) had mucosal irregularity, 16 patients (22.85%) had secretions. External compression was seen in 12 patients (17.14%).

Table 5: Bronchoscopy Finding

Bronchoscopy finding	Numbers	Percentage
Normal	24	35%
Mucosal Irregularity	4	5.71%
Secretions	16	22.85%
Growth	14	20%
External compression	12	17.14%

Figure 2: FOB finding

Twenty-four patients had same sided mediastinal shift. Fourteen (58.3%) out of the twenty four patients with same sided mediastinal shift had endobronchial growth on fob. No growth was found in the rest 10 patients. Seventy patients with exudative

effusion were subjected to FOB. Normal lavage cytology was present in 60% of patients. Twelve patients (17.14%) had malignant cytology positive BAL. Sixteen patients (22.85%) had CBNAAT positive BAL.

Table 6: Bronchoscopic BAL cytology and biopsy

Diagnosis	Numbers	Percentage
Normal cytology	42	60%
Malignant	12	17.14%
AFB / CBNAAT +ve	16	22.85%
Total	70	100%

Seventy patients with exudative effusion were subjected to FOB. Normal finding or external compression was seen in 51.42% of patients (p value 0.06). Malignancy was detected in 25.72% patients (p value was 0.04). Tuberculosis was found in 22.85% of patients (p value was 0.05).

Table 7: Diagnostic yield of both Pleural fluid analysis and Bronchoscopy

Diagnosis	Bronchoscopy	P Value
Normal Bronchoscopy+external compression	36(51.42%)	0.06
Malignant	18 (25.72%)	0.04
Tubercular	16 (22.85%)	0.05
Total	70 (100%)	0.05

Thirty four out of 70 patients had bronchoscopic finding (18 malignancy +16 tuberculosis). We found that among the 18 patients with neoplastic origin in FOB, 10 patients had haemoptysis as symptom (55.5%). Among the 16 patients who had tubercular etiology, 8 had haemoptysis (50%)

Table 8: Occurrence of haemoptysis

Diagnosis	haemoptysis	No haemoptysis	total
Malignancy	10(55.5%)	8(44.6%)	18(100%)
Tuberculosis	8(50%)	8(50%)	16(100%)

Figure 3:

Discussion

In this study out of 70 patients Endobronchial growth was found in 14 patients(20%), mucosal irregularity in 4 patients (5.71%), CBNAAT positive lavage in 16(22.85%). So FOB can be a useful less invasive tool before opting for a more invasive procedure like thoracoscopy. Eighteen out of these 34 patients (52.94%) had haemoptysis as clinical presentation. Thus haemoptysis can be an important clinical clue for selecting patients who

can have bronchoscopic finding. Other indications of FOB in pleural effusion can be massive effusion without mediastinal shift and infiltrates on CXR.

We also found that haemorrhagic effusion, low glucose and effusion with ipsilateral mediastinal shift were other predictors of malignant effusion. In this study all the patients with CBNAAT positive BAL had ADA value 20 to 30. Williams and Thomas evaluated the role of FOB. In his study twenty eight patients with pleural effusion of

undetermined etiology. In this group, 4 patients had a diagnostic FOB. The authors concluded that FOB was of value in the Evaluation of patients with undiagnosed pleural effusion. In their group, all three patients with malignancy Presented with hemoptysis.[6] Fiberoptic Bronchoscopy and Pleural Effusion of Unknown Origin by Steven H. had diagnoses of malignancy in 29 percent of cases and Idiopathic pleural effusion in 46 percent [5]

In the study by Albert and Braman 28 patients with unexplained pleural effusion after pleural fluid analysis and pleural biopsy (UPE), only one FOB demonstrated malignancy, despite a final diagnosis of tumor in seven.[5] Our study had better yield in diagnosing TB which might be attributed to the fact that TB is much more prevalent in our country and a small sample size.

The Diagnosis of Pleural Effusions by Fiberoptic Bronchoscopy and Pleuroscopy study by T. Williams and P. Thomas had 11/28 patient's positive FOB finding.[6] Shi-Chuan Chang, Reury-Perng Perng also concluded in their study that Bronchoscopy is justifiable in effusion patients with haemoptysis or pulmonary infiltrates.[7]

They also remarked that Closed and regular follow-up may be enough for some patients and occasionally, empirical anti tubercular treatment may be given to patients with positive tuberculin skin test or clinical feature favouring tuberculosis[7]. Though pleural biopsy and medical thoracoscopy (gold standard) remain the ideal next step for such patients but both are more invasive in nature .So bronchoscopy can be an alternate less invasive approach, particularly in patients where malignancy is a possibility (smoker, elderly, haemoptysis, haemorrhagic effusion).

Conclusion

We evaluated the usefulness of fiber optic bronchoscopy in determining the etiology of undiagnosed exudative pleural effusion. FOB may be an useful initial non-invasive tool in such patients, before opting for a more invasive procedure like thoracoscopy, which carries a substantially more mortality risk. We concluded that the yield of bronchoscopy is more if patient has endobronchial symptom like haemoptysis. So haemoptysis can be an important clinical clue to select patients for FOB.

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